

Contrast Enhancement Method for MRI and X-ray Images Based on a Modified Entropy Curve

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Abstract- MRI and X-ray images are widely used for detecting various prevalent diseases, and accurate diagnosis heavily depends on image quality. Often, images suffer from low contrast due to factors such as uneven or insufficient illumination, motion of the subject or imaging device, and device-related imperfections, some- times accompanied by noise or artifacts. In such cases, an effective contrast enhancement algorithm that improves visibility without amplifying noise or artifacts becomes crucial. In this work, we propose a simple yet efficient contrast enhancement method for medical images, based on dividing a modified entropy curve into two sub-entropy curves and combining it with homomorphic filtering. The proposed approach enhances image contrast while preserving important details and minimizing noise amplification. The effectiveness of the method is demonstrated through comprehensive qualitative and quantitative evaluations, highlighting its potential for improving medical image analysis.

Keywords – Image enhancement, Entropy curve, Homomorphic Filtering.

I. INTRODUCTION

Low-contrast medical images may lead to an inaccurate diagnosis of a disease which may be dangerous for the patient's health condition. Medical images are often obtained by applying electromagnetic (EM) waves to the human body and recording the response. The repeated exposure to EM waves is harmful to the human body so multiple image capturing is not recommended. Also, sometimes medical images do not have sufficient contrast and detail due to technical issues present in devices, movement of patient during the time of image capturing, and some other unfavorable conditions present in the lab, etc. That's why it becomes very necessary to improve the contrast and details of the medical images without increasing the artifacts and noise to detect any disorder present in the human body.

There are many methods available in the literature to serve this purpose. Histogram equalization (HE)[1,2] is one of the most basic and widely used methods due to its simple implementation. At the same time, the HE method does not have any mechanism to control the enhancement level. Also, the mean intensity of the enhanced image is always middle grey level. This problem is called the mean shift problem. It causes unnecessary visual degradation. Several HE-based methods have been developed by various researchers to overcome these shortcomings and improve the contrast through various mechanisms. Some of them are based on histogram partition, dynamic histogram equalization, and histogram clipping.

To counter the mean shift problem, a technique proposed by Yeong-Taeg et al. [3] (named BBHE) is based on dividing the histogram into two sub-histograms based on the average intensity of the input image. In this technique, each sub-histogram is equalized separately using the HE method and these equalized sub-histograms are combined to achieve the enhanced image. In this method mean intensity of the enhanced image lies between the mean value of the input image and the middle grey level. Wang et al. [4] proposed a method named DSIHE.

This method is similar to BBHE with the only difference being that the histogram is split based on the median value of the image. It also claims that DSIHE preserves the mean brightness better than BBHE and contains information better than BBHE. Later Chen et al. [5] generalized the BBHE and developed a technique named RMSHE, in this technique each sub-histogram is divided further into two sub-histograms recursively on the bases of the mean intensity of each sub-histogram. This process repeats until the optimal enhancement does not achieve. Similarly, a generalization of DSIHE is suggested by Sim et al. [6] (named RSIHE) in this technique each sub-histogram is divided further into two sub-histogram recursively on the bases of the median intensity of each sub-histogram.

The above methods RMSHE, and RSIHE are time-consuming due to their iterative nature. The main drawback of these methods is that using these methods' number of sub-histograms one can construct 2^n where n is the number of iterations. As a result, most of the time we are unable to get the optimum

enhancement level in the output image. An image without proper enhancement can cause difficulty in the identification of the disease.

To counter these drawbacks (such as mean shift problem, and recursive segmentation of the histogram) (Mayank Tiwari et al. [7]) developed a non-recursive method named HSQHE. In this technique, any number of histogram partitions can be constructed. To achieve the enhanced image, apply histogram equalization on each constructed sub-histograms and combine this equalized sub-histogram. HSQHE divides the histogram based on quantile value without using recursive segmentation. This technique enhances the image without affecting the mean brightness of the image and it requires less time than other approaches due to its non-recursive nature.

All the above mentioned methods enhance the contrast and are able to preserve the mean brightness of the image up to a certain level. At the same time, these methods do not work very well for those images having spikes in the intensity histogram. These spikes appear in the histogram mainly due to the smooth regions in the image. During the equalization process, these spikes influence the rate of the enhancement, which is defined as follows:

$$\Delta f(X_k) = f(X_k) - f(X_{k-1}) = (X_{L-1} - X_0)P[X_k], \quad (1)$$

and is proportional to the probability of occurrence of grey level in the image $P(X_k)$. Therefore all less frequent gray levels are dominated by higher frequent gray levels. Thus, areas of the image with high probable gray levels see over-enhanced, and areas of the image with lower probable gray levels see less enhanced. This may cause the image to lose important visual information. Since every piece of information is very important in the field of medical imaging. To preserve visual information and control the enhancement level Kim et al. [8] proposed a method RSWHE, in this technique author assigned a slightly larger weight to less frequent grey levels and a slightly lower weight to more frequent grey levels in accordance with the power law function. The main benefit of RSWHE is that it preserves image brightness while enhancing image contrast. This method also uses a recursive process to divide the histogram into sub-histograms. The RSWHE method is modified in accordance with some specific requirements [9-15]. Huang et al. [16] proposed a technique (AGCWD), the adaptive gamma correction and weighting distribution function is employed in this technique. This technique automatically boosts the brightness of dimmed images.

The AGCWD is easy and enhances the contrast of the input image. However if the input image doesn't have enough bright pixels, it can not produce good results. To overcome these drawbacks Joseph et al. [17] developed a method on the basis of the histogram clipping process. In this method, a clip limit applies to the histogram. This method controls the enhancement

level up to some extent. However, in this method, the clipping threshold value is set manually and varies from image to image. Therefore it can be very difficult to find a clipping threshold value at which optimal enhancement can be achieved. C.Ooi et al.

[18] suggested a technique BHEPL, which controls the enhancement level by using a clipping limit on the intensity histogram. C. S. Sarada et al. [19] proposed a technique named (DQHEPL). In this method histogram is divided into four sub-histogram after that to control enhancement plateau limit is applied to each sub-histogram. Clipped each sub-histogram equalized and combine this equalized sub-histogram to achieve the output image.

All the methods mentioned above are not able to improve the contrast locally, hence sometimes important hidden information may not come out. To improve the contrast locally, Zuiderveld. K. et al. [20] proposed a technique named CLAHE, in this technique image is divided into small blocks, and improves the contrast locally, and combines each block. Finally, we get the enhanced image. At the same time, it increases noise and artifacts for medical images. For CT images Ameen et al. [21] modified the CLAHE with the help of normalized gamma modification. The modification in CLAHE is done by adding an initial phase of a normalized gamma correction function. Iqbal et al. [22] developed a technique for enhancing low-resolution medical images based on dual-tree complex wavelet transform (DT-CWT).

This technique uses non-local means filter and singular value decomposition. It generates fewer artifacts than the conventional discrete wavelet transform (DWT) [23]. Yang et al. [25] proposed a technique, in this method DWT and soft thresholding schemes are used to improve the quality of images. For the X-ray and natural images Ming Zeng et al. [26] proposed a method, in which the input image is divided into some equal-sized regions on the bases of the intensities of gradients. After this, develop a new version of the histogram was called the grey-level information histogram. To achieve an enhanced image HE or CLAHE is applied on this new histogram. Zhao et al.

[27] designed a technique to enhance the MRI image, X-ray images, and CT images based on luminance-level modulation and gradient modulation. Kallel et al. [24] designed a technique for low-contrast CT images based on adaptive gamma correction and DWT-SVD. This method does not work very well for other kind of medical images [28,29,30,31]. For medical images, Jianglan Wang et al. [32] developed a method named Retinal fundus image enhancement with image decomposition and visual adaptation. In this method, images are separated into different frequency channels with the help of the total variation (TV) based texture decomposition method in the base layer and detail layers. As the detail layer mainly

contains useful information and the base layer contains noise and other information. Therefore, in this method, we carefully enhance the detail layer with no changes to the base layer and combine it with the base layer to obtain the enhanced image.

Among all the above-discussed methods in the literature for contrast enhancement, we observed that these methods do not improve sufficient contrast. Sometimes, the resultant image has the under/over enhancement in dark/bright regions. Hence, a loss of information takes place in these regions. Therefore we need to develop a method that does not lose any information in the dark or bright regions. Since different types of medical images have different kinds of problems and constraints, we start with a brief discussion on them in order to understand the problem to achieve an efficient solution. Here, we consider only the limitations of X-ray, and MRI images.

We develop an algorithm for medical images based on the entropy curve of images that utilizes the complete information associated with grey levels. The efficiency of this method is proven by qualitative and quantitative analysis.

II. PROPOSED METHOD

In this section, we describe the proposed technique based on the entropy curve modification of the image. The flow chart of the proposed method is shown in Fig. 1. In the proposed method, we initially find the entropy corresponding to each gray level and we plot these entropy values against the gray level to obtain the entropy curve of the image. After that, we obtain the modified entropy curve of the image with the help of the entropy curve and uniform entropy curve. Finally, we equalized the modified entropy curve and apply homomorphic filtering in order to reduce the content of noise in the enhanced image.

Entropy curve

The idea of entropy curve is similar to the intensity histogram of the image, in the entropy curve instead of frequency we plot entropy against the corresponding grey level of the image. Now to draw the entropy curve, let us assume that G be an image of size $M \times N$ then the entropy of that image is just the expected value of the information I contained in that image

$$H = E[I(X)] = E[-\log_2(P(X))],$$

$$H = - \sum_{X \in \chi} P(X) \log_2(P(X)),$$

where $I(X)$ is the information of the image, X is the grey-level of the image and χ is domain of X . $P(X)$ represents the probability that a pixel take the grey-level X .

In order to draw an entropy curve we required that the entropy of different grey levels of the image, let E_i be the entropy of the i th grey level. Then E_i is define as follows:

$$E_i = \sum_{t \in \Omega} I_i(t) P(t=i) \log_2(P(t=i)),$$

$$I_i(t) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{when } t = i, \\ 0 & \text{else.} \end{cases}$$

where

Ω is the domain of grey level/intensity and the values of Ω from 0 to 255.

$$E_i = -P_i \log_2(P_i), \tag{2}$$

where P_i is the probability of occurrence of the grey level i at any pixel.

In simple words, E_i is the information associated with the i th grey level. In order to obtain the entropy curve, we plot E_i values against the i th grey level.

Uniform entropy curve

Let I will be an $M \times N$ image i.e image has MN number of pixels. For the uniform probability of the grey-level, we distribute MN pixels uniformly in 256 grey levels.

Number of pixel in each grey level is

$$PX_u = \frac{MN}{256},$$

uniform probability corresponding to each grey level is

$$P_u = \frac{PX_u}{MN},$$

$$P_u = \frac{1}{256},$$

then entropy corresponding to grey level is defined as

$$E_u = -P_u \log_2(P_u), \tag{3}$$

entropy E_u is called uniform entropy because of corresponding to each grey level entropy is same. By plotting the uniform entropy values of various grey levels against the grey levels uniform entropy curve is derived. It is denoted by EU .

$$E_u(i) = E_u \quad 0 \leq i \leq 255 \tag{4}$$

Step 1. Entropy curve Modification:

Let E be the entropy curve of the input image and EU be the uniform entropy curve. Then modified entropy curve E' is obtained by the equation (5)

$$E' = \alpha E + (1 - \alpha) E_u, \tag{5}$$

where $0 \leq \alpha \leq 1$.

Equation (5) is an optimization problem and our aim is that we choose α without much affecting the information of an image in such a way that difference between E' and EU is very small and gets optimum enhancement.

Modified Entropy Curve Equalization:

In this section, we equalized the modified entropy curve with the help of transformation function given in equation (6)

$$TF = X_0 + (X_{L-1} - X_0) \text{cdf}, \quad (6)$$

where X_0 and X_{L-1} are lowest and highest intensity level of histogram respectively and cdf is cumulative distribution function.

The probability distribution function (pdf) for each modified entropy curves is denoted by pdf and are defined as

$$pdf = \frac{E(l)}{SM} \text{ for } 0 \leq l \leq L-1, \quad (7)$$

where SM is the total entropy value (i.e sum of entropy against each grey level in modified entropy curve) of modified entropy curves. The cdf for modified entropy curve is calculated as

$$cdf(l) = \sum_{k=0}^l pdf \text{ for } 0 \leq l \leq L-1. \quad (8)$$

The transformation function is given as

$$T = (L-1) \times cdf. \quad (9)$$

To the enhanced image applying the above transformation function obtained by equation (9) to the input image, a contrast-enhanced image is obtained.

Figure 1: Flow chart of the proposed method

Step 2. Homomorphic Filtering:

Generally, the contrast enhancement process results in a simultaneous increase in contrast as well as noise. To reduce the content of noise in some visually important areas, we use homomorphic filtering. The homomorphic filter is the most famous and important type of nonlinear filter. It can remove the multiplicative noise and can be effectively used for images that have uneven illumination. The flow chart of the homomorphic filtering is shown in Fig. 2 The homomorphic filter uses the illumination-reflectance model. In this model digital images consider as the product of the illumination and reflection component. Then image can be defined as

$$S(x, y) = sr(x, y) \times si(x, y). \quad (10)$$

In equation (10), $S(x, y)$ is the original image. $si(x, y)$ is the illumination component and $sr(x, y)$ is the reflection component. Since, the illumination component has small variance, which means it is composed mostly by low frequency components [37]. While, the reflection is mainly composed of high frequency components, which is the detail of the image [37]. We extract the reflectance component from the image by eliminating the influence of the illumination component. In order to apply filter we transform the image to the frequency domain. The normal signal and noise we want to separate is a linear combination, however this time the two components are multiplied. It is not convenient to work on illumination and reflection respectively, so we apply the logarithmic function in eq.(10) to change the product expression into additive expression:

$$\ln(S(x, y)) = \ln(si(x, y)) + \ln(sr(x, y)), \quad (11)$$

$$M(x, y) = I(x, y) + R(x, y), \quad (12)$$

here, we represent $\ln(S(x, y))$, $\ln(si(x, y))$ and $\ln(sr(x, y))$ by $M(x, y)$, $I(x, y)$ and $R(x, y)$ respectively. the high-pass filter is applied to $M(x, y)$,

$$N(x, y) = H(x, y)M(x, y), \quad (13)$$

here $N(x, y)$ lies in frequency domain.

Now we use the Fourier inverse transformation to $N(x, y)$ to map the signal back to spatial domain

$$n(x', y') = \text{IDFT}(N(x, y)). \quad (14)$$

The wanted reflection component is recovered as

$$s_r(x', y') = \text{en}(x', y'). \quad (15)$$

Finally, we get the output image as

$$F(x', y') = s_r(x', y')si(x', y').$$

The following formula is used to apply image normalization after homomorphic filtering-

$$g(x^{\wedge}, y^{\wedge}) = X_{(M1/X_{MO})}F(x^{\wedge}, y^{\wedge}), \quad (16)$$

where the mean brightness of the input image is represented by XMI and the image after homomorphic filtering is represented by XMO.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, we evaluate the efficiency of the proposed method based on various measures and compare it with state-of-the-art methods. For this, we conduct quantitative and qualitative assessments. As qualitative assessment is measured through visual perception and depends on the fact that how a person perceives the distortion, which may differ from person to person. On the other hand, it happens many times that the low-quality image gives better metric values. Hence, we cannot tell about the efficiency of the method by any single assessment. Thus both have equal importance. Therefore, to prove the efficiency of the proposed method, we use both quantitative and qualitative assessments. For this purpose, we apply the proposed method to different types of images presented in Fig. 3 and the standard dataset. The contrast enhancement methods with which we compare the proposed method are HE [1,2], CLAHE [20], Ref. [24], and Ref. [38]. Here, we choose these methods because of their specific feature. As HE is used for overall contrast enhancement and CLAHE is used to enhance the contrast locally. Ref. [24] and Ref. [38] are used to control the enhancement level.

Figure 2: X-ray images are in the first column and denoted by Img.1, Img.2, Img.3, and Img.4 from top to bottom. MRI images in the second column and denoted by Img.5, Img.6, Img.7, and Img.8 from top to bottom.

IV. QUANTITATIVE ASSESSMENT

To evaluate the efficiency of the proposed method through quantitative assessment, we use Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR)[39], Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM) [40], Gradient Magnitude Similarity Deviation GMSD [41], and Entropy [2] quality measurement. A lower value of GMSD indicates better performance of the algorithm, a higher value of the other measures indicates better enhancement and a higher value of entropy indicates that more information is associated with the image.

SSIM

SSIM is a perception-based model that considers image degradation as a perceived change in structural information. Structural information is the idea that pixels have strong interdependencies, especially when they are spatially close. These dependencies hold important information about the structure of the objects in the scene view. The SSIM value ranges from 0 to 1 and is used to analyze the degree to which the processed image is structurally similar to the original image. The enhanced image quality in terms of structural similarity depends on how close the SSIM value is to 1. If the value of SSIM is very close to 1, then the processed image is very similar to the original image in terms of structure.

The mathematical equation of SSIM is given below

$$SSIM(x, y) = \left(\frac{(2 \mu_x \mu_y + a_1)(2 \sigma_{xy} + a_2)}{(\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + a_1)(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + a_2)} \right)$$

where a_1 and a_2 are constant. Here pixel sample mean of x and y are μ_x and μ_y respectively and defined as

$$\mu_x = \frac{1}{N} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{j=N} x_j \right)$$

$$\mu_y = \frac{1}{N} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{j=N} y_j \right)$$

variance of x and y is defined as

$$\sigma_x = \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^{j=N} (x_j - \mu_x)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

$$\sigma_y = \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^{j=N} (y_j - \mu_y)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

covariance of x and y is defined as

$$\sigma_{xy} = \frac{1}{N-1} \left(\sum_{j=1}^{j=N} (x_j - \mu_x)(y_j - \mu_y) \right),$$

GMSD

Xue et al.[41] developed an algorithm to measure their performance of algorithm is known as Gradient Magnitude Similarity Deviation (GMSD). It is calculated by taking standard deviation of gradient magnitude similarity (GMS) at each pixel of an image. To the mathematical equation, $m_r(i)$ is the magnitudes of gradients of the reference image r and $m_d(i)$ is the magnitudes of gradients of the distorted image d at the pixel position j . Then the GMS is calculated by following the equation

$$GMS(j) = \frac{2m_r(j)m_d(j) + c}{m_r^2(j) + m_d^2(j) + c}$$

where c is a positive constant.

Now we obtained the value of GMSM (Gradient magnitude similarity mean) by taking the mean of GMS.

$$GMSM = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^{j=N} GMS(j),$$

hence,

If the value of GMSD is low range than it shows that the enhanced image is less distorted and has better visual perception.

$$GMSD = \left(\frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^{j=N} (GMS(j) - GMSM)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}},$$

PSNR

PSNR is the peak signal noise ratio and this ratio is used to measure the re-constructive quality of the enhanced image. The higher PSNR value indicates that the reconstruction of the image is done with higher quality [36,37,38,39]. The PSNR value is calculated by the following formula

$$PSNR = 10 \log_{10} \frac{(L-1)^2}{MSE},$$

here MSE is calculated by the equation given below

$$MSE = \frac{1}{MN} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{i=M} \sum_{j=1}^{j=N} (X(i, j) - Y(i, j))^2 \right),$$

The mean square error is the difference between the pixel values of the original and resultant images. The higher value of PSNR shows that reconstruction of the image is better than other methods.

Entropy value for different methods

Entropy is used to measure how accurately the image appears. If the value of entropy is large then this indicates that more information is available in the image. The mathematical formula to calculate entropy of an image is given as:

$$E = - \sum_{i=0}^{L-1} p_i \log_2(p_i),$$

where i is the grey level.

From Table 1, the value of PSNR is higher than other histogram-based techniques. A higher value of PSNR shows that the proposed algorithm is the better re-constructive algorithm. Hence we can conclude that the enhanced image obtained by the proposed technique closely resembles the original. From Table 2, the value of SSIM is higher than other histogram-based techniques.

This shows that the performance of the proposed technique is better than other histogram-based techniques in the context of structural similarity. The higher value of SSIM also shows that enhanced images are less degraded in the context of structural similarity i.e. enhanced image is very similar to the original image in the context of structure. From Table 3, the GMSD value of the proposed technique is lower than other histogram-based techniques. This shows that the performance of the proposed technique is superior to other histogram-based techniques and this also shows that the enhanced images obtained by the proposed technique are less distorted. From Table 4, the value of entropy is higher than in other histogram based methods. Hence, the enhanced image obtained by the proposed method contains more details (information).

Thus, from the above discussion, it is clear that the proposed method gives the lowest value of GMSD and gives a higher value of SSIM, entropy, and PSNR as compared to other algorithms. Hence the performance of the proposed method is better than other techniques on the images presented in Fig. 3.

Analyzing a small set of images is not sufficient to demonstrate an algorithm's performance. The enhancement algorithm may fail in one or more circumstances due to the random disparity of the images. Consequently, the suggested approach is justified over some standard data set of images. For this purpose, we evaluated the performance of the proposed method over all the X-ray images of COVID-19 data set Ref [42], the all the mammogram images (2534) of data set Ref.[43] and all the MRI images taken from data set Ref. [44]. The average values of GMSD, entropy, SSIM, and PSNR of all X-ray, mammogram and MRI images taken from the datasets are presented in Table 5, Table 6, and Table 7 respectively. From Tables 5, 6 and 7, it is clear that the proposed technique

Table 1: PSNR Values for different method

Sr no	HE	CLAHE	Ref. [38]	Ref [24]	proposed method
Img.1	16.3521	14.3847	19.2072	15.7365	19.482
Img.2	9.2635	17.5947	26.3650	12.4980	32.2080
Img.3	19.2517	19.8077	18.4084	12.3888	20.3627
Img.4	14.0502	17.0662	15.4351	13.1766	21.7003
Img.5	10.8754	16.9219	20.8416	19.5813	27.9694
Img.6	15.6440	17.5541	17.1023	15.9059	18.8503
Img.7	2.0156	19.9028	19.6832	7.8395	29.7706
Img.8	6.4775	18.8857	26.2545	6.2189	27.1034
mean	12.4059	17.4968	20.7469	13.9916	26.1178

Table 2: SSIM Values for different method

Sr no	HE	CLAHE	Ref. [38]	Ref. [24]	proposed method
Img.1	0.6591	0.5957	0.8937	0.6502	0.7742
Img.2	0.4094	0.7011	0.6508	0.5889	0.9358
Img.3	0.8016	0.8815	0.8381	0.7680	0.8595
Img.4	0.7779	0.7094	0.6745	0.8540	0.8526
Img.5	0.5917	0.6955	0.5753	0.8111	0.9217
Img.6	0.7441	0.6817	0.7584	0.7341	0.8556
Img.7	0.0754	0.1430	0.3664	0.1062	0.4839
Img.8	0.3219	0.3322	0.8915	0.3071	0.5519
mean	0.5607	0.5997	0.7384	0.6152	0.8160

has the highest value of SSIM over the large dataset. This shows that enhanced images are less degraded in the context of structural similarity. Hence, the enhanced image is very similar to the original image in the context of structure. The value of GMSD is lower than other techniques. Hence, we can conclude that the performance of the proposed technique is better than other histogram-based techniques. The higher value of entropy shows that the enhanced images obtained by proposed method have more information. The PSNR value is also the highest, hence proposed algorithm is the better reconstructive algorithm.

Table 3: GMSD Values for different method

Sr no	HE	CLAHE	Ref.[38]	Ref. [24]	proposed method
Img.1	0.1793	0.2002	0.0874	0.0868	0.1201
Img.2	0.2856	0.1252	0.0696	0.2626	0.0354
Img.3	0.0078	0.0551	0.0745	0.0246	0.0405
Img.4	0.1321	0.1396	0.0610	0.0836	0.0632
Img.5	0.2478	0.1598	0.1309	0.2043	0.0498
Img.6	0.1178	0.1455	0.1288	0.1173	0.0842
Img.7	0.1476	0.1124	0.0993	0.1226	0.0167
Img.8	0.0777	0.1455	0.0455	0.1001	0.0321
mean	0.1490	0.1351	0.0849	0.1273	0.0463

Table 4: Entropy Values for different method

Sr no	HE	CLAHE	Ref.[38]	Ref. [24]	proposed method
Img.1	5.3038	6.7850	6.3441	7.1472	7.0008
Img.2	4.6985	6.7142	5.2036	7.0560	6.7517
Img.3	5.7241	7.1454	6.0928	5.9761	7.7415
Img.4	5.9298	7.6680	6.6242	7.6579	7.6137
Img.5	5.0576	6.8391	5.9467	6.3651	7.1702
Img.6	5.9492	7.3071	6.7767	7.8838	7.8676
Img.7	1.2560	2.3336	1.9483	1.8371	3.7403
Img.8	3.1909	4.6949	4.2741	3.9191	6.4134
Img.9	5.7634	7.2728	6.2932	7.6124	6.8338
mean	4.7703	6.3556	5.5467	6.1263	6.7473

Table 5: Average metric value Of all the X-ray images of COVID-19 data set Ref. [42]

Sr no	HE	CLAHE	Ref.[38]	Ref.[24]	proposed method
SSIM	0.7634	0.7186	0.7354	0.7748	0.8590
Entropy	5.7913	7.3277	6.3597	7.1347	7.4894
PSNR	16.6093	16.9607	17.0921	15.8612	19.9450
GMSD	0.1014	0.1439	0.1235	0.1077	0.0705

Table 6: Average metric value all the MRI images taken from data set Ref. [44]

Sr no	HE	CLAHE	Ref. [38]	Ref.[24]	proposed method
SSIM	0.4682	0.5382	0.8089	0.2225	0.8170
Entropy	4.8946	6.7590	2.6379	2.0234	6.9056
PSNR	11.1550	16.9766	23.0721	10.2345	27.9918
GMSD	0.2047	0.1702	0.0660	0.2034	0.0536

V. QUALITATIVE ASSESSMENT

Sometimes quantitative analyses are not sufficient to prove the efficiency of the proposed method because the low-quality image may give better metric values as we have already

discussed. Therefore, qualitative evaluation is very necessary to evaluate the efficiency of the proposed technique. This can be achieved by visual perception. To serve this purpose, the proposed technique has been applied to several images presented in Fig. 3 taken from the data set given in Ref [42], Ref. [43], and Ref. [44].

Here, we have compared the results of the proposed technique with state-of-the-art techniques for qualitative analysis. The methods we compare are HE, CLAHE, Ref. [24], and Ref. [38], and a visual comparison is shown in Figures 9 to 12. It is clear from Figure 9 that the enhanced images obtained by HE are over-enhanced and lose the information in dark and bright regions. The enhanced images obtained by CLAHE have noise and artifacts. The enhanced images obtained by Ref. [24] contains noise and has blurriness. This can be easily seen in the enhanced image. Enhanced image obtained by Ref. [38] is over-enhanced and contains artifacts. This can be easily seen in the enhanced image of Img.3. While the proposed method enhances the X-ray images properly and there are no artifacts or noise in the enhanced images. It also preserves the naturalness of the images.

Fig. 10 shows a comparison of mammogram images. From Fig. 10, it is clear that the enhanced images obtained by histogram equalization are over-enhanced in dark or bright regions. The enhanced images obtained by CLAHE are over enhanced in dark or bright region and has the artifacts in background parts of images. Improved images obtained by Ref. [24] loses the some information in the bright or dark regions. The enhanced image obtained by Ref.[38] is not properly enhanced. It can also be clearly seen in Figure 10 that the artifacts, noise, and blurriness are also visible in the enhanced images. While the proposed method improves mammogram images properly and there is no artifacts or noise in the enhanced images. It also preserves the naturalness of the images.

A comparison of the MRI images is shown in Fig. 11. From Figure 11, it is clear that the enhanced images obtained by HE are over-enhanced in bright or dark regions. These enhanced images have noise and some artifacts. Enhanced images obtained by CLAHE also do not have sufficient detail and noise is present in enhanced images. The improved images obtained by Ref.[24] contain noise. The enhanced image obtained by Ref. [38] is over-enhanced and contains artifacts. While the proposed method enhances the MRI images properly and there are no artifacts or noise in the enhanced images. It also preserves the naturalness of the images.

From the Fig.12, It can be concluded that X-ray images (Img.4) are over- enhanced by CLAHE and have more artifacts and noise. The enhanced image of Img.7 obtained by Ref. [24] is over-enhanced in the bright regions (presented in Fig.11) while the proposed method enhances the properly. The enhanced image of Img.11 obtained by Ref. [38] is over-enhanced in the

bright regions (pre- sented in Fig.12). Some noise, and artifacts are also observed in the enhanced image while the proposed method enhances the properly without any noise and artifacts. In the whole assessment, we choose the value of α empirically. The empirical value of α is 0.55 for which we are achieving best results.

From the above discussion we can conclude that the proposed method is better than other methods. Thus, by the qualitative and quantitative analyses, it is clear that in the proposed algorithm optimum enhancement level is obtained in the image without any artifacts and noise. It also preserved the natural characteristics of the image. Hence from the above, it can be concluded that the proposed algorithm is the most conventional and gives better results. Thus, the efficiency of the proposed technique is proved by qualitative and quantitative analyses.

Figure 3: In figure, the original image[42], entropy curve of original image, and histogram of original image is in top row. The output image entropy curve of enhanced image, and histogram of enhanced image in second row

Figure 4: In figure, the original image [42], entropy curve of original image, and histogram of original image is in top row. The output image entropy curve of enhanced image, and histogram of enhanced image in second row

Figure 5: In figure, the original image [44], entropy curve of original image, and histogram of original image is in top row. The output image entropy curve of enhanced image, and histogram of enhanced image in second row

Figure 6: Visual comparison of original image and enhanced images is given above from top to bottom indicate, original image (1) HE (2) CLAHE (3), Ref. [38] (4), Ref. [24] (5), proposed

Figure 7: Visual comparison of original image and enhanced images is given above from top to bottom indicate original image (1), HE (2) CLAHE (3), Ref. [38] (4), Ref. [24] (5), proposed

Figure 8: Visual comparison of original image and enhanced images is given above from top to

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the contrast enhancement method has been proposed based on the entropy curve. The proposed technique is developed to preserve brightness and improve the details and contrast of MRI, and X-ray images. It uses a modified entropy curve to improve detail and contrast without increasing noise and artifacts. Experimental results based on human visual perception and quantitative analysis show the superiority of proposed techniques over the standard and state of art contrast enhancement methods.

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